

Communication Toolkit

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WP6 – D6.2

D6.2: Communications Toolkit			
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Checked			
Approved			

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Introduction

The goal of the NPHyCo project is assess the potential for developing large scale, low-carbon, hydrogen production facilities linked to nuclear power plants. This includes identifying potential locations where a demonstration project could eventually be built.

Interaction with relevant stakeholders plays an essential part in the development of projects. This includes informing them about the project and its outcomes, as well as providing them with the possibility of engaging with the partners and discussing and thoughts and feedback which they may have.

As part of the communication and dissemination strategy the following aspects need to be taken into account:

- To transfer knowledge and innovation gathered to different stakeholders and to receive their feedback.
- To investigate if and how public awareness/acceptance about nuclear power is impacted, when linked to H2 generation.
- To identify education and training needs, including using this project to encourage more young people to join the sector.
- To connect / network to related other sectors or industries.
- To market / advertise pilot projects in the next phase.

The NPHyCo project will run over a period of 2 and a half years. In order to ensure that the communication strategy is aligned with the outcomes of the project, and that the communication needs of the different stakeholders are met, this plan is to be seen as a flexible tool which will be amended on a regular basis to ensure the best possible outcome of communication actions.

Communication Toolkit

Visual Identity

In order to provide the project with a clear visual identity a logo has been developed. The fonts and colours used form the basis of all communication tools.

Logo:

Colour codes:

Based on this, the following tools have been produced and made available to the Partners

Flyer

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WP1: Conceptualisation

This Work Package will focus on conceptualisation of the project. This includes

- Identifying the needs and benefits hydrogen produced from nuclear
- Ensuring that any research undertaken addresses the challenges faced by nuclear power plants appropriately
- Prepares for the implementation of the Pilot Project

WP2: Technical Roadmap

This Work Package will focus on the technical conditions related to the coupling of a hydrogen production facility to an existing NPP. This includes identifying:

- The needs of a hydrogen plant
- The services and resources of an existing NPP which could be shared with the hydrogen facility
- Interactions between the two facilities

WP3: Economic Roadmap

This Work Package aims to develop a business plan for hydrogen produced from nuclear power. This includes:

- Economic feasibility of such projects
- Estimating potential costs and revenues
- Identifying the market needs for low-carbon hydrogen & how nuclear can help meet demand
- Economic comparison between nuclear and other hydrogen production sources

WP4: Licensing Roadmap

This Work Package will focus on licensing requirements. This includes:

- Identification of key licencing issues to be considered when planning a hydrogen facility couple to an NPP
- Defining ways in which the licensing process can be optimised

WP5: Implementation Road map

This Work Package will put forward proposals for pilot plant locations and their layout. This includes:

- Development of criteria to assist in the identification of the most suitable concept
- Review of the technical and economic solutions identified by WPs 2 + 3 to assist in the implementation of pilot projects
- Conducting an integration assessment once the pilot project location is identified

WP6: Communication, Dissemination & Public Awareness

This Work Package focuses on communication around the project. This includes:

- Sharing the outcomes of the project with stakeholders and getting feedback
- Assessing how such projects affect public acceptance
- Identifying potential education and training needs

WP7: Project Coordination & Management

PowerPoint presentation

PRESENTATION TITLE

Name, Job title - Organisation
Date

About NPHyCo

- EU research project dedicated to the production of hydrogen from nuclear power
- Funded by the EU's Euratom Research & Training programme (2021-2025) dedicated to nuclear research and innovation
- Kicked-off in the Autumn of 2022 and will run for two and a half years

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The Challenge

- Full decarbonisation of the EU's economy by 2050
- Could hydrogen be part of the solution? Potentially yes BUT
 - to date most of the hydrogen produced in Europe comes from fossil fuels
- How can Europe:
 - Ramp up production of low-carbon hydrogen?
 - Produce to meet demand?
 - Ensure it is affordable?

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Project goals

- NPHyCo will focus on the potential for developing large scale, low-carbon, hydrogen production facilities linked to nuclear power plants.
- It will start by assessing the feasibility of producing hydrogen near an existing nuclear power plant as well as the added value of such project.
- It will also look at potential locations where a pilot project could be implemented.

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Work Packages

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Work Packages

WP5: Implementation Roadmap

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- Review of the technical and economic solutions identified by WPs 2 + 3 to assist in the implementation of pilot projects
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WP6: Communication, dissemination & public awareness

This Work Package focuses on communication around the project. This includes:

- Sharing the outcomes of the project with stakeholders and getting feedback
- Assessing how such projects affect public acceptance
- Identifying potential education and training needs

Project Partners

Thank you!

www.nphyco.eu

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Word Template

DOCUMENT TITLE

Name, Job title - Organisation

Date

WP - Task

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This toolkit can be found on the FLEXX Platform (Under WP6 – D6.2 [Communication toolkit](#)).

Furthermore, a dedicated NPHyCo website has been produced: www.nphyco.org

A [LinkedIn](#) page has also been created.

Partners are encouraged to make use of all these tools in order to promote the project in a consistent and harmonised way.

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Conclusion

In order to ensure a timely communication of the project, it is important to maintain a close interaction with the different WPs to have a clear overview of results which are expected and when. These can then be communicated via the project website and LinkedIn page. Furthermore, partners are encouraged to keep the WP6 leader informed of any communications actions in order to ensure trace of all activities for reporting purposes.

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